

Preliminary Assessment of the Emissions-reduction Potential at Unchanged Performance of a Second-generation Biofuel in Historic Engines

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Abstract. The energy transition requires a rapid reduction in the use of fossil fuels, finite resources whose combustion generates substantial greenhouse-gas emissions. Within Europe, transport alone accounts for roughly one third of total greenhouse-gas emissions, with road transport being the predominant component. Euro standards were therefore introduced to mandate reductions in key pollutants, including CO and NO_x. In addition to electronic emission-control systems and exhaust aftertreatment, a range of innovative fuels is spreading, notably biofuels. However, most studies in the literature assess the performance of various fuels on modern or motorcycle engines, not on historic carbureted engines. The latter are particularly significant in Italy given the large, aging historic vehicle fleet. The main historic-vehicle federations advise caution and the use of low-ethanol formulations so as not to damage elastomers, fuel tanks, and carburetor float bowls. For this reason, few suppliers have developed fuels specifically for classic vehicles. Among this minority, in 2023 Coryton Advanced Fuels introduced the SUSTAIN Classic line, including the Super 80 variant. In the present study, the performance, fuel consumption, and emissions of an air-cooled, four-stroke Fiat 500 engine fueled with commercial RON 95 gasoline and Coryton SUSTAIN Classic Super 80 were analyzed. A first test comprised a complete sweep from 1000 to 5000 RPM and a second test evaluated four different main jets at maximum torque and maximum power. From the experimental observations, it is inferred that the biofuel can replace gasoline without appreciable penalties in torque, power, or fuel consumption; however, while CO emissions are reduced, NO_x emissions increase.

Keywords: heritage vehicle, biofuel, engine performance, exhaust emission, sustainability

1. Introduction

Fossil energy sources, besides being finite resources, are the main cause of global warming. Human activities have already produced an average temperature increase of 1.1 °C in the decade 2011–2020 relative to 1850–1900 and rapid emission reductions are needed to meet the 2050 targets [1]. In the European context, transport accounted for 29% of total greenhouse-gas emissions in 2022, with road transport predominant at 73%, and passenger cars representing the largest share [2–3].

Beyond greenhouse gases, road mobility emits various pollutants. In particular, the Euro emission standards have reduced CO, NO_x, HC, and PM compared with 1990, yet emissions from transport remain a concern, especially in urban areas. To counter these emissions, multiple solutions are spreading, shifting to less-polluting modes (rail or ship), electrification (BEV/PHEV), hydrogen, e-fuels, and biofuels. As of 2023, the share of renewable energy in EU transport is 10.8%, equal to 20.9 million tonnes of oil equivalent (Mtoe), 88.5% of which consists of biofuels [4–5].

Much of the experimental literature on fuel performance concerns modern engines with electronic control units or motorcycle applications, not historic carbureted powertrains. The Italian context makes the latter studies particularly relevant, as the country has one of the largest and oldest historic vehicle fleets in Europe

[6]. In 2024 Italy had over 41 million registered passenger cars with an average age of 13 years, about one quarter of which are still Euro 0–3 [7–8].

Added to this are compatibility issues between E10 fuels and materials used in legacy fuel systems—such as elastomers, fuel tanks, and float bowls—especially in vehicles subjected to long periods of inactivity. Indeed, the main historic-vehicle federations recommend caution and the use of low-ethanol formulations [9]. In response, few suppliers have developed gasoline specifically for classic vehicles. Among these is Coryton Advanced Fuels, which in 2023 introduced the SUSTAIN Classic line, including the Super 80 variant. The technical documentation indicates a free-ethanol content below 1%, a feature aimed at compatibility with historic systems.

The present paper therefore compares the torque, power, fuel consumption, and CO and NO_x emissions of an air-cooled, four-stroke, two-cylinder Fiat 500 engine fueled with commercial RON 95 gasoline and with Coryton SUSTAIN Classic Super 80. The testing campaign was carried out on the engine test bench of the LINEA Laboratory at the University of Florence. Two types of tests were conducted: (i) a 1000–5000 RPM sweep with a 110 main jet for both fuels, and (ii) a comparison at maximum torque and maximum power using four different main jets (108, 110, 115, 120) for both fuels.

This study aims to provide quantitative evidence for the practicality of second-generation biofuels as solutions to reduce the emissions impact of the historic vehicle fleet without costly system modifications, within the European framework in which renewable energy in transport is growing and remains largely driven by biofuels.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Characteristics of biofuels

2.1.1 Generations of biofuels

Biofuels are classified by generation according to the origin of the feedstock and the maturity of the supply chains. First-generation (1G) biofuels are produced from edible crops. These include bioethanol, obtained by fermenting sugars or starches, and FAME (Fatty Acid Methyl Esters) biodiesel, produced by transesterification of vegetable oils.

Second-generation (2G) biofuels use lignocellulosic residues and by-products, such as agricultural straw, forest residues, and the organic fraction of municipal solid waste. They can yield cellulosic ethanol, synthetic diesel via gasification followed by Fischer–Tropsch synthesis, and renewable gasoline obtained from bio-based intermediates [10].

Third-generation (3G) biofuels are based on high-productivity algal feedstocks, a technology that is still maturing from both the technical and economic standpoints [11–12].

The comparison of environmental impacts is carried out through Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), a resource-to-wheel estimate that covers feedstock supply, conversion processes, distribution, and in-vehicle use. Recent reviews highlight wide variations among studies, driven primarily by assumptions about agricultural yields, the electricity mix, and direct and indirect land-use change.

2.1.2 Reduction of greenhouse gases

On average, 1G fuels reduce emissions relative to gasoline only when land-use change does not occur. The magnitude of the benefit also depends on the feedstock. Sugarcane ethanol shows substantial reductions, whereas corn ethanol is more variable and sensitive to assumptions about agriculture and co-product allocation.

2G fuels achieve larger reductions—often on the order of 60–80% versus gasoline—because they lessen reliance on dedicated crops and their associated impacts by using residues and waste fractions [11].

3G pathways have high potential but today exhibit significant energy use in cultivation and dewatering, which diminishes the climate advantage if process energy is not renewable [12].

2.1.3 Energy use

Over the life cycle, 1G fuels are particularly affected by process energy for fermentation/distillation and by agricultural inputs (fertilizers, on-farm diesel). In 2G pathways, biomass pretreatment and the hydrolysis or thermochemical conversion stages can increase process energy demand [11]. For 3G biofuels, cultivation, separation, and drying of algal biomass strongly affect cumulative energy demand [12].

2.1.4 Water use

The water footprint of 1G fuels is high and highly dependent on the crop and local climate. Global assessments report ranges from 1,400 liters up to 20,000 liters of water per liter of biofuel, with generally lower values for ethanol from sugar beet or potato, and higher values for biodiesel from jatropha or rapeseed.

By contrast, 2G fuels show lower water footprints in comparable contexts because they are based on agricultural residues that do not require dedicated cultivation [13]. For 3G fuels, water needs for cultivation and separation can be very high unless configurations use wastewater or well-optimized closed systems [12].

2.1.5 Land use

Impacts depend on prior land use and the crop. Conversions to 1G crops are associated with declines in species richness and abundance at the local scale and, in many cases, biodiversity losses exceed those linked to fossil gasoline or diesel when land-use change is included. However, perennial crops or plantations on marginal lands tend to show less negative effects. For 2G fuels, the use of residues reduces direct pressure on habitats and alleviates the need for new cultivated areas [14–15]. For 3G fuels, the evidence is still consolidating and is highly site-dependent [16].

2.2 Coryton SUSTAIN Classic Super 80

Coryton Advanced Fuels is a European manufacturer specializing in bespoke fuels that, in 2023, presented to the public the SUSTAIN line. The three SUSTAIN Classic fuel types (Super 80, Super 33, Racing 50) were showcased as the first sustainable gasoline available in the UK for historic vehicles that requires no engine modifications [17]. The Super 80 variant used in this study is a blend consisting of 70–85% renewable C5–C10 hydrocarbons obtained via catalytic conversion of ethanol and 10–25% ETBE used as an additive, as shown in the table below.

SUSTAIN Classic Super 80

Safety Data Sheet

according to the REACH Regulation (EC) 1907/2006 amended by Regulation (EU) 2020/878

3.2. Mixtures			
Name	Product identifier	%	Classification according to Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008 [CLP]
Renewable hydrocarbons (naphtha type fraction) obtained from the catalytic transformation of ethanol. Predominantly rich in aromatic and saturated hydrocarbons with a carbon number range from C5 to C10.	EC-No.: 701-193-0 REACH-no: 01-2120790169-43	70 – 85	Flam. Liq. 1, H224 Skin Irrit. 2, H315 Muta. 1A, H340 Carc. 1A, H350 Repr. 2, H361d STOT SE 3, H336 Asp. Tox. 1, H304 Aquatic Chronic 2, H411
ETBE	CAS-No.: 637-92-3 EC-No.: 211-309-7 REACH-no: 01-2119452785-29	10 – 25	Flam. Liq. 2, H225 STOT SE 3, H336

Full text of H- and EUH-statements: see section 16

Table 1. Original safety data sheet for SUSTAIN Classic Super 80

The fuel lists a density of 0.753 kg/L, a flash point of -40 °C, and a boiling point of 201 °C. It has a RON 98 octane rating and an ethanol content below 1%, useful for limiting corrosion and material-compatibility issues in historic fuel systems. The manufacturer attributes to Super 80 a reduction of at least 65% in greenhouse-gas emissions relative to fossil gasoline, which appears consistent with the use of agricultural-waste feedstocks typical of second-generation fuels [18].

Similar effects have been reported in another study in the literature, in which ethanol and a pyrolysis-derived biogasoline obtained from low-grade waste were evaluated as additives to commercial gasoline (RON 95, RON 98) in tests carried out on a late-1990s engine.

The results showed that engine torque, power, and overall efficiency remained essentially unchanged compared with neat gasoline, while HC and CO emissions decreased. In contrast, the findings on NO_x emissions were inconclusive, as some test conditions exhibited higher values than the base gasoline and others lower values [19].

2.3 Renewables in transport in the European Union

2.3.1 Renewables and biofuels

In the EU transport sector the share of renewables reached 10.8% in 2023, an increase of 1.2 percentage points (p.p.) over 2022 (9.6%). In energy-volume terms for 2023, an estimated 20.9 Mtoe of renewable energy was used in transport, of which 18.5 Mtoe (88.5% of all renewables used in the sector) came from biofuels [4–5].

Within this total, biodiesel increased by 5.7% year on year across the European Union, reaching 14.3 Mtoe, equivalent to 77.3% of all biofuel consumption. Beyond biodiesel, bio-gasoline grew by 5.6%, equivalent to 3.5 Mtoe. The largest increase occurred in Italy, followed by Austria and Germany [4]. As for biomethane, its consumption rose by 13.4% relative to 2022, reaching 558.8 ktoe. In 2023, Italy led bio-gasoline consumption with growth of about 140%, equal to 49 ktoe. Growth was also recorded for biomethane, supported by policies that favored its use in the transport sector [4, 20].

2.3.2 Main rules to decarbonise transport

European Climate Law (Reg. (EU) 2021/1119) makes legally binding the EU's climate-neutrality goal for 2050 and a net emissions reduction of at least 55% by 2030 compared with 1990 [21]. The Fit for 55 package translates these targets into sectoral measures for transport (road, aviation, maritime) and energy [22]. For transport, three main elements are particularly relevant:

(i) Fuel Quality Directive (FQD 98/70/EC). It set a maximum sulphur content of 10 mg/kg for unleaded petrol and diesel placed on the market and, with the 2009 revision, introduced a 6% reduction in the greenhouse-gas intensity of fuels by 2020 relative to 2010 [23].

(ii) Renewable Energy Directive (RED III). In transport, the 2023 revision replaces the previous single target with two equivalent options for Member States: by 2030 either achieve at least a 14.5% reduction in the greenhouse-gas intensity of transport fuels, relative to a baseline defined in the act, or reach a renewables share of at least 29% in final transport energy consumption [24].

(iii) Emissions targets. In road traffic, the vehicle fleet remains the main source of NO_x at the EU level [25].

Between 1990 and 2022, transport emissions nevertheless declined: NO_x –51%, SO₂ –82%, CO –90% and CH₄ –76%. Over the same period, transport emissions of particulate matter—including non-exhaust sources—with aerodynamic diameters ≤10 μm (PM₁₀) and ≤2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) fell by 46% and 58%, respectively [26].

For CO₂, the standards for cars and vans (Reg. (EU) 2023/851) set fleet-wide targets for new vehicles of –55% for passenger cars and –50% for light commercial vehicles by 2030 relative to 2021 values, and a 100% reduction relative to the 2021 target from 2035 for both categories [27].

2.4 Transport emissions and laws in Italy

In Italy, transport emissions increased by 6.7% from 1990 to 2023. In 2023 the sector accounted for 28.3% of the national total, compared with 26.6% in 2022. For 2023, 92.6%, equal to 100,928.3 kt CO₂eq, of transport emissions came from road transport [28–29]. Specifically, road transport accounts for 40.2% of national NO_x, 14.9% of CO, 9.8% of PM₁₀, and 8.9% of PM_{2.5} [30]. The high emission pressure stems from a large and aging vehicle fleet. In 2023, Italy is estimated to have 694 passenger cars per 1000 inhabitants, the highest rate in the EU, where the average is 571. By Euro standard, in 2023 the largest share is Euro 6 (36%), followed by Euro 0–3 (25%), Euro 4 (22%), and Euro 5 (16%). Notably, Euro 0–3 vehicles still make up one in four cars on the road—models that are at least 18 years old [31–32].

In 2023, it is estimated that for passenger cars 84.0% of total car-kilometres were driven by conventionally fueled vehicles (28.3% gasoline and 55.7% diesel), 7.0% by LPG, 1.7% by natural gas, 5.5% by gasoline–electric hybrids, 0.9% by diesel–electric hybrids, and 0.8% by battery-electric cars [33]. The effort to reduce the impact of the oldest part of the fleet is advancing on two fronts: restrictions on circulation in the most critical urban areas through Low-Emission Zones (LEZs) with Euro-class rules, and fuel policies to increase the renewable share in the marketed blend [34].

On the second front, Italy has transposed RED II through Legislative Decree 199/2021 and applies an obligation on suppliers to place minimum shares of sustainable biofuels on the market, managed via

Certificates of Release for Consumption (CIC). In addition, the Ministerial Decree of 15/09/2022 supports the production of biomethane for transport with grants and incentive tariffs to strengthen the national supply chain [35].

2.5 Tested engine: Fiat 500 engine with code 110F.000

The experimental activity was carried out on the engine model used in the Fiat 500 F (engine code 110F.000). The tested engine—first produced in 1965—is a four-stroke, two-cylinder, spark-ignition engine. The main characteristics are presented in the table below.

Engine Type	Spark-ignition, air-cooled
Strokes for cycle	4
Number of cylinders	2
Displaced volume	499.5 cm ³
Firing order	1-2
Engine speed range	1000 RPM ÷ 5000 RPM
Maximum power	13 kW @ 4250 RPM
Maximum torque	30.4 Nm @ 3000 RPM

Table 2. Summary of the main engine features

In order to reduce emissions compared to the previous engine, the 110F.000 engine adopted a blow-by device, which draws the combustion gases that leak between the piston and the cylinder and redirects them into the intake manifold to be burned again. The valve timing is of the OHV (Overhead Valves) type, meaning that the valves are housed in the cylinder head in an overhead position, while the camshaft is located in the crankcase.

Ignition is handled by a distributor, while the fuel system relies on an inverted single-body Weber 26 IMB 4 carburetor, with a venturi diameter of 21.00 mm and a main jet of 1.12 mm. The cooling system is forced-air and uses a centrifugal fan located inside the housing. A portion of the air is directed under the oil pan to cool its temperature.

2.6 Tools used

Before setting up the engine on the test bench, two functional modifications were carried out:

- One spark-plug seat was restored using a helical insert to ensure proper coupling and sealing of the instrumented spark plug.
- A phase reference was created by removing one tooth from the trigger wheel (missing tooth) for the unambiguous identification of Top Dead Center (TDC) and the synchronization of the combustion and speed signals.

The engine was tested on an eddy current test bench of 110 kW maximum power and 11000 RPM maximum rotating speed. The crankshaft is coupled directly to the brake via an elastomeric pin coupling, which dampens the torsional pulsations of the twin-cylinder. Torque and power were measured directly at the crankshaft output. Figure 1 shows the picture of the engine placed on the test bench.

Figure 1. Fiat 500 engine at the test bench

To control the throttle opening of the carburetor from the control station, an actuator was used. The fuel mass flow rate was measured with the AVL PLUTRON CLASSIC volumetric flow meter. The air-fuel ratio was monitored with a Bosch LSU 4.9 UEGO lambda sensor, while the intake air temperature was acquired with a type-T thermocouple.

The temperature and pressure in the test cell were likewise monitored to standardize the results. To measure the in-cylinder pressure trace, a Kistler instrumented spark plug was used, which allows for the determination of the pressure trend in the combustion chamber without having to drill the cylinder. The angular measurement procedure utilizes the missing tooth and a Hall-effect sensor facing the trigger wheel: the missing tooth generates a discontinuity in the square wave that enables both revolution counting and TDC marking. Exhaust emissions are detected with the Assemblad multi-gas analyzer, which measures CO, NO_x, CO₂, O₂, and HC.

2.7 Source of fuels

Conventional 95-octane gasoline was obtained at a service station near the laboratory. By contrast, the SUSTAIN Classic Super 80 biofuel was supplied directly by Coryton Advanced Fuels. The exact composition of the latter fuel was not disclosed, as it is a trade secret. On the other hand, some characteristics are available in the safety data sheet shown in Table 1.

3. Results

3.1 Experimental procedure

All the data acquired during the tests were recorded following the same procedure. For each point, the speed was set electronically and, once the set-point had been reached, the measured values were allowed to stabilize, with particular attention to lambda. The measurement was recorded over a 30-second window, after which an averaged point over that time interval was determined. Two different campaigns were carried out:

- **Campaign 1.** With main jet 110, a complete sweep from 1000 RPM to 5000 RPM was performed using both fuels, starting with the biofuel. Data were taken every 250 RPM. Between 1750 RPM and 2500 RPM only the value at 1875 RPM was recorded because it was not possible to stabilize the engine.

- **Campaign 2.** Four main jets (108, 110, 115, 120) were tested at 3000 RPM (maximum torque) and 4250 RPM (maximum power). As for the order of the tests, all main jets were tested first with the biofuel and then with 95-octane gasoline, repeating the same conditions.

Figure 2. The main jet installed in the carburetor (circled in red)

3.2 Checking data consistency

Before processing the results, a consistency check was carried out on the data recorded at 3000 RPM and 4250 RPM using the same 110 main jet in both tests to ensure the repeatability of the operating conditions. As shown in tables 3 and 4, the observed differences were within 1.5%, confirming the absence of systematic errors and the comparability of the two test campaigns.

	Sweep_STD	Sweep_BIO	110 main jet_STD	110 main jet_BIO
Engine speed [rpm]	3000	3000	3000	3000
Torque [Nm]	28.404	28.696	28.253	28.503
Power [kW]	8.933	9.057	8.885	8.996
	Torque [Nm]_STD	Power [kW]_STD	Torque [Nm]_BIO	Power [kW]_BIO
Sweep Value	28.404	8.933	28.696	9.057
110 main jet Value	28.253	8.885	28.503	8.996
Results [%]	0.53	0.54	0.67	0.67

Table 3. Comparison at 3000 RPM (maximum torque)

	Sweep_STD	Sweep_BIO	110 main jet_STD	110 main jet_BIO
Engine speed [rpm]	4250	4250	4250	4250
Torque [Nm]	23.961	23.768	23.866	23.421
Power [kW]	10.65	10.565	10.608	10.41
	Torque [Nm]_STD	Power [kW]_STD	Torque [Nm]_BIO	Power [kW]_BIO
Sweep Value	23.961	10.65	23.768	10.565
110 main jet Value	23.866	10.608	23.421	10.41
Results [%]	0.4	0.4	1.48	1.49

Table 4. Comparison at 4250 RPM (maximum power)

3.3 Campaign data analysis 1

3.3.1 Torque and power at the crankshaft

The trends for 95-octane gasoline and SUSTAIN Classic Super 80 biofuel are essentially overlapping across the entire RPM range considered. Torque increases up to 2750 RPM for gasoline and up to 2500 RPM for the biofuel, while power rises up to 4000 RPM for both fuels. The largest relative difference in both torque and power occurs at 4750 RPM, with values of 1.64% and 1.63%, respectively. Therefore, within the studied range, the biofuel does not penalize performance, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Trends of torque and power for both fuels from 1000 RPM to 5000 RPM using a 110 main jet

3.3.2 Brake Specific Fuel Consumption (BSFC)

Figure 4 shows that the conventional fuel (gasoline) exhibits a lower BSFC under standard operating conditions, indicating a more efficient conversion of its chemical energy into useful mechanical work compared with the biofuel. The highest efficiency is observed between 3000 RPM and 3500 RPM, where gasoline ranges from 345 g/kWh to 360 g/kWh, while the biofuel ranges from 354 g/kWh to 359 g/kWh, resulting in a disadvantage for the biofuel of 2.38% at 3000 RPM and 4.15% at 3500 RPM. At higher speeds, the relationship reverses: the biofuel's improvement is linked to a leaner mixture, as shown by both the lambda value and the CO levels. In particular, at 4250 RPM the relative difference is 7.86% and at 4750 RPM it is 34.97%, both to the advantage of the biofuel.

Figure 4. Trends of BSFC for both fuels from 1000 RPM to 5000 RPM using a 110 main jet

3.3.3 Lambda (λ) and exhaust emissions data

Figure 5 shows that lambda is moderately rich between 1000 RPM and 1250 RPM, exhibits a lean peak between 1250 RPM and 1875 RPM, remains near the stoichiometric value between 2500 RPM and 4000 RPM, and then becomes rich again at higher speeds. The biofuel tends to run leaner over the entire range, with relative differences between the two fuels of 1.11%, 3.13%, and 4.72% at 2750, 3500, and 4750 RPM, respectively.

CO is minimal where lambda is approximately stoichiometric and is lower with the biofuel across nearly the whole range. The largest difference between the fuels is 61.85% at 3500 RPM, when both are very close to stoichiometric. Only at 1250 RPM does gasoline show a lower value than the biofuel, with a relative difference of 17.97%.

NOx is highest where lambda is near stoichiometric and is greater with the biofuel, especially above 4250 RPM, consistent with the slightly leaner mixture and higher peak temperatures (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Trends of lambda for both fuels from 1000 RPM to 5000 RPM using a 110 main jet

Figure 6. Trends in CO emissions (left y-axis) and NOx emissions (right y-axis) for both fuels from 1000 RPM to 5000 RPM using a 110 main jet

3.4 Campaign data analysis 2

3.4.1 Temperature

Figure 7 presents the trend of the mean cylinder-head temperature, measured with a thermocouple positioned near the base of the spark plug, for the two fuel types as a function of the main jet employed. The temperatures remain essentially stable as the main jet changes, ensuring that the operating conditions during the tests were comparable.

Figure 7. Cylinder-head temperature trends for both fuels at 3000 RPM (solid line) and 4250 RPM (dashed line), using the four main jets

3.4.2 Torque and power at the crankshaft

Figure 8 shows that the torque profiles of the two fuels are essentially overlying. The relative differences between the fuels range from 0.2% to 2.3% at peak torque and from 0.3% to 1.9% at peak power. Figure 8a indicates that at 3000 RPM torque increases with main jet size, as expected. The maximum value is 29.1 Nm, measured with the 120 main jet using the biofuel. Conversely, at 4250 RPM the maximum torque, 23.9 Nm, is observed with the 110 main jet using gasoline. With larger jets the torque tends to decrease, indicating that a greater fuel quantity does not improve performance (Figure 8b).

Figure 8. Torque trends of the two fuels at (a) 3000 RPM (maximum torque) and (b) 4250 RPM (maximum power)

Power mirrors the torque trends with respect to differences between fuels. At 3000 RPM the values increase with jet size and coincide at 115, reaching 8.95 kW, as shown in figure 9a. Figure 9b shows that at 4250 RPM gasoline exhibits a peak of 10.61 kW with the 110 main jet followed by a slight decrease, whereas the SUSTAIN Super 80 fuel increases up to the 120 main jet, at which 10.55 kW is reached.

Figure 9. Power trends of the two fuels at (a) 3000 RPM (maximum torque) and (b) 4250 RPM (maximum power)

3.4.3 Indicated Mean Effective Pressure (IMEP)

IMEP is consistently higher with gasoline at a given engine speed and main jet size, indicating more work per cycle. At maximum torque, the relative differences between the fuels across the jets range from 5.82% with the 120 main jet to 7.86% with the 108 main jet. At maximum power, they range from 5.24% to 6.75% with the 120 and 115 main jets, respectively (Figure 10).

Figure 10. IMEP trends of the two fuels at 3000 RPM (solid line) and 4250 RPM (dashed line)

3.4.4 Fuel consumption and Brake Specific Fuel Consumption (BSFC)

Figure 11 shows that fuel consumption increases with main jet size for both fuels and is generally higher with the biofuel. At maximum torque, the relative differences between the fuels are 3.13%, 3.79%, 3.35%, and 9.12% for main jets of 108, 110, 115, and 120, respectively. The same trend is confirmed at maximum power, since a larger main jet admits a greater quantity of fuel and biofuels tend to have a lower heating value than gasoline, resulting in less energy available per unit mass and therefore higher consumption.

Figure 11. Fuel consumption trends for the two fuels at 3000 RPM (solid line) and 4250 RPM (dashed line)

BSFC is generally lower for the standard fuel, indicating better conversion efficiency. At maximum torque, the relative differences between the two fuels are 2.91%, 2.38%, 3.15%, and 6.42%, while at maximum power they are 0.77%, 6.27%, 4.23%, and 6.19% for main jets of 108, 110, 115, and 120, respectively (Figure 12). For both fuels, BSFC increases with larger main jets, indicating that the higher fuel flow is not offset by a proportional increase in power. The most pronounced penalty occurs for the biofuel with the 120 main jet, when the effect of its lower heating value becomes even more evident because more fuel mass is used.

Figure 12. BSFC trends for the two fuels at 3000 RPM (solid line) and 4250 RPM (dashed line)

3.4.5 Lambda (λ) and exhaust emissions data

Figure 13 shows that as the main jet size increases, the mixture becomes richer, whereas for a given jet size the biofuel tends to run leaner. Across the different main jets, the relative difference between the two fuels ranges from 2.58% to 5.07% at maximum torque and from 3.05% to 6.70% at maximum power.

Figure 13. Lambda trends for the two fuels at 3000 RPM (solid line) and 4250 RPM (dashed line)

Consistent with the lambda trend, CO increases with increasing main jet size for both fuels, although the biofuel systematically shows lower values. The relative differences between the fuels range from 14.52% to 153.6% at maximum torque and from 17.10% to 63.20% at maximum power, with the largest gap observed with the 108 main jet in both cases (figure 14).

NOx exhibits the well-known inverse trend relative to CO. Levels are higher when the mixture is near stoichiometric and the biofuel is used. The relative variations range from 27.65% to 37.85% at maximum torque and from 16.95% to 50.97% at maximum power (Figure 15). The biofuel thus shifts the balance toward more complete combustion, leading to lower CO alongside higher NOx.

Figure 14. CO emission trends for the two fuels at 3000 RPM (solid line) and 4250 RPM (dashed line)

Figure 15. NOx emission trends for the two fuels at 3000 RPM (solid line) and 4250 RPM (dashed line)

4. Conclusions

This study assessed changes in performance and emissions of the four-stroke, two-cylinder, spark-ignition Fiat 500 F engine. The engine was tested using conventional 95-octane gasoline and the second-generation biofuel Coryton SUSTAIN Classic Super 80. Using the same data-acquisition method based on a steady-state 30-second window, two tests were conducted: (i) a sweep from 1000 to 5000 RPM with a 110 main jet for both fuels; (ii) a comparison of four main jets (108, 110, 115, 120) at 3000 RPM (peak torque) and 4250 RPM (peak power). Inter-campaign repeatability was within 1.5%, ensuring data comparability.

On the performance side, the torque and power trends for the biofuel are largely overlapping with those for gasoline across the full speed range and at the two key operating points with the four main jets. IMEP is ~6% higher with gasoline across the various jet–speed combinations, indicating slightly more work per cycle. Regarding fuel-to-power conversion efficiency, BSFC shows modest deviations up to 4250 RPM and diverges at higher speeds, to the disadvantage of gasoline.

On the emissions side, the usual CO–NOx trade-off driven by lambda is evident. The biofuel significantly reduces CO relative to gasoline, with reductions up to 61,85% at 3500 RPM, while NOx is higher, with increases of about 50% above 4000 RPM. It follows that Coryton SUSTAIN Classic Super 80 is fully suitable in vintage engines lacking electronic control, with no significant penalties in torque, power, or fuel

consumption compared with gasoline. The biofuel offers a marked benefit in CO at identical setup, although it results in an expected increase in NO_x.

Future work will enforce identical lambda for the two fuels and optimize the biofuel calibration above 4000 RPM to contain NO_x while maintaining a sufficient advantage in CO. Further studies on larger-displacement vintage engines could be carried out to quantify performance and emissions differences between the two fuels when a greater fuel quantity is used per combustion cycle.

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